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CAIRT Level 2 ATBD

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This document shall describe the mathematical algorithms for the CAIRT retrieval. As the specifics of the retrieval processes are not finalised, yet, it introduces the general concepts and algorithms needed to create a (tomographic) level 2 process. The focus is on extending the well known techniques for 1-D limb sounding retrievals such as described by Carli et al. (2020) by algorithms capable of dealing with large-scale 2-D and even 3-D tomographic retrievals. As such, we presently do not repeat the large amount of still very relevant material contained in (Carli et al. 2020) here, but focus on advancements in the technique necessitated by large-scale tomographic retrievals.</p>		
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1 Introduction

This document shall describe the mathematical algorithms for the CAIRT retrieval. As the specifics of the retrieval processes are not finalised, yet, it introduces the general concepts and algorithms needed to create a (tomographic) level 2 process. The focus is on extending the well known techniques for 1-D limb sounding retrievals such as described by Carli et al. (2020) by algorithms capable of dealing with large-scale 2-D and even 3-D tomographic retrievals. As such, we presently do not repeat the large amount of still very relevant material contained in (Carli et al. 2020) here, but focus on advancements in the technique necessitated by large-scale tomographic retrievals.

2 The (inverse) problem

The level 2 processing of CAIRT needs to solve a so called inverse problem. While it is rather straightforward to simulate measurements (using a so called forward model) given an atmospheric state, there is no easy way to do the reverse. In practice, one iteratively modifies the atmospheric state intelligently until the simulated measurements agree with the actual ones within reason.

Mathematically speaking, we have an atmospheric state $f \in L^2$ and a forward model $F: L^2 \mapsto \mathbb{R}^m$, which maps the atmospheric state f onto a discrete set of $m \in \mathbb{N}$ measurements. The forward model is of a physical nature and comparatively simple to compute. There is however no analytical or practical inverse to F . The inverse problem is then to identify the atmospheric state f , which fits to a given set of measurements y .

$$F(f) \stackrel{!}{=} y$$

This problem is often ill-posed such that, due to measurement noise in y or short-comings of F (which is only an approximation) no f exists that perfectly fits the measurements, or that noise in y has a determining influence on the result. As such, instead a minimization problem is solved:

$$\min_f \|F(f) - y\|_2^2,$$

where the Euclidian norm of the discrepancy between simulated measurements and actual measurements is minimized. The Euclidian norm chosen as it is the most fitting for the types of measurement errors normally encountered. Still, the influence of noise can be rather large, in particular if the measurements do not fully constraint the solution, which often necessitates the addition of an additional constraint $\Phi(f)$, which is discussed in detail in Chap. 6. Thus, the complete problem can be written as:

$$\min_f \left(\|F(f) - y\|_2^2 + \Phi(f) \right)$$

As practical necessity for a computer program, the function f will need to be represented by a discrete vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, on which the forward model F will operate. Also, the measurement error in y will be taken into account by a random variable $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and a covariance matrix S_ϵ , i.e.

$$\min_x \left(\|S_\epsilon^{-1/2}(F(x) - y)\|_2^2 + \Phi(x) \right)$$

is the final problem to solve.

Chapter 3 will detail the employed discretisation from f to x , while Chap. 5 will detail the setup of S_ϵ . Chapter 6 will talk about the setup of Φ . Finally, Chap. 7 will describe how to solve the resulting discrete minimization problem.

Generally, this document will focus on the efficient implementation of algorithms for large-scale retrievals with n in the order of several ten thousands of elements and beyond.

We follow largely the mathematical style of Rodgers (2000) with some notations borrowed from Tarantola (2004), in particular where the treatment of the continuous problems f is discussed.

3 Discretization

The continuous atmospheric field f must be discretized to a finite-dimensional representation to be representable in a computer. Considerations for choosing a proper discretization are the conflicting requirements of minimisation of misrepresentation errors due to the finite discrete approximation on the one hand, and having a small set of discrete samples and basis functions with small support to reduce computational complexity on the other hand.

For one dimensional atmospheres, one typically uses a vertical sampling, either regular or aligned to tangent point locations, with linear interpolation in between (using logarithmic interpolation for certain quantities such as pressure) (Carli et al. 2020).

A two-dimensional field can be discretized in a similar manner. To allow for an efficient and fast interpolation, rather relevant for tomographic retrievals, a rectilinear representation is advantageous, with one dimension being altitude over the WGS84 spheroid and the other being the along-track distance (e.g. Press et al. 2007). Typically, one also requires an atmospheric state for values outside the defined two-dimensional plane. Similar to the assumption of horizontal homogeneity taken for 1-D retrievals, one assumes homogeneity in across-track direction. I.e. points away from the 2-D plane need to be projected horizontally onto the plane along a vector of shortest distance, where a normal 2-D interpolation can derive a value (similar to how one assumes horizontal homogeneity for 1-D retrievals, one assumes here homogeneity in across-track direction).

Other representations are feasible, e.g. splines or primary components, but the wide supports of these basis functions causes the number of non-zeros in the derivatives of the forward model to increase drastically, increasing memory consumption and computational complexity drastically. Another option would be to use the location of tangent points; this irregular grid would require, e.g., Delaunay triangulations for interpolation and would also require a costly regridding due to the changing locations of tangent points due to refraction when temperature or water vapour are fitted. In addition to this, the benefits are marginal for a tomographic retrieval (in contrast to traditional 1-D retrievals such as used for MIPAS), where the information at a tangent point is *not* mostly defined by its associated measurement (the one which determined the tangent point location) but equally by a several preceding and succeeding measurements.

Figure 1: Schematic of the geometry of a limb sounder. The rays are straight (unless refracted at lower altitudes below 30km) and the surface is curved. Retrievals are typically performed in a geo-coordinate system with an along-track and an altitude coordinate as shown in the next figure.

Figure 2: An exemplary 2-D regular grid in combination with one line-of-sight. Blue points marks points of the grid (not according to specification). The points needed for the bilinear interpolation for this line-of-sight are marked in orange. Please note the curvature of the line-of-sight due to the employed coordinate system.

Figure 2 shows an example with a fully regular grid. To identify the atmospheric state at any point along the line of sight the four surrounding points are identified and a bilinear interpolation is executed.

Figure 3: Seeing the tracks and line-of-sights from above. Different 2-D plane are marked in green, three line-of-sights for the center and the outermost assumed tracks are shown.

For tracks away from the center, the line-of-sights are not within a 2-D plane due to the curvature of the earth and the observation geometry of the instrument. The extent of this depends on the altitude range of the retrieval, the track width and the horizontal swath width. The effect of this is small but should be diagnosed as an across-track displacement of the retrieved values (e.g. by computing a 3-D/2-D averaging kernel as in Ungermann et al. (2011, Sect. 3.2)).

4 The forward model

The forward model has the task of simulating the radiances measured by the instrument given a discretized atmospheric state. It need not be fully physically accurate, but can take approximations as long as these do not lead to unacceptable errors in the level 2 results. For example, typically not all constituents of the atmosphere need be considered in a simulation, if their effect can be approximated by an additional simplified fit parameter such as a general "extinction" or "offset". Whether or not an approximation is acceptable can typically only be determined by retrieval studies including error analysis and, often, the evaluation of actual measurement data. However, there is a lot of experience from past missions, one can build on.

Here we report the analytical expressions of radiative transfer and typical instrumental effects so-called 'physics-based' or 'line-by-line' models like the Karlsruhe Optimized and Precise Radiative Transfer Algorithm (KOPRA) are based on. With few adaptations, this chapter is based on chapter II of Stiller (2000). We show the formal expressions of the equation of radiative transfer in the atmosphere, the source function for local thermodynamic equilibrium as well as non-local

thermodynamic equilibrium conditions, transmission, slant path column densities of molecules, ray tracing, absorption and extinction coefficients, line intensities as function of temperature, line shape functions, instrument line shape of an interferometer, numerical apodization, aperture effects, and field of view consideration.

4.1 Introduction

Computational treatment of radiative transfer processes in the atmosphere requires numeric treatment of many processes. Nevertheless, the analytic expression behind the numerics actually coded is important to make a code understandable. The intention of this paper is presentation of these analytical expressions, such that interrelations of variables used (e.g. in the KOPRA program) become traceable. In the following, first radiative transfer physics is discussed in a top to bottom manner, starting with the radiative transfer equation, and consecutively breaking it down to more detail. Second, the degradation functions of a Fourier transform spectrometer with finite field of view as well as numerical apodization are explained.

4.2 Radiative Transfer Equation

The general equation of radiative transfer in the atmosphere includes absorption, emission and scattering of light. Its differential form is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS_{\theta}(v, l)}{dl} = & -\left(\sigma_a^{vol}(v, l) + \sigma_s^{vol}(v, l)\right) S_{\theta}(v, l) \\ & + \sigma_a^{vol}(v, l) J(v, l) \\ & + \sigma_s^{vol}(v, l) \frac{1}{4\pi} \iiint_{4\pi} S_{\theta'}(v, l) P(v, l, \theta, \theta') d\theta' \end{aligned}$$

where

S_{θ}	spectral radiance for the viewing direction θ
J	source function (see Section 4.2.2)
dl	path element (see Section 4.2.1)
σ_a^{vol}	absorption coefficient (per volume) (see Section 4.2.3.1)
σ_s^{vol}	scattering coefficient (per volume) (see Section 4.2.3.1)
$P(v, l, \theta, \theta')$	phase function (probability of radiation coming from direction θ' to be scattered in direction of θ)
ν	wavenumber
l	path coordinate

For cases where scattering can be neglected, i.e. for radiative transfer in the mid-infrared or microwave in purely gaseous atmospheres or, in general, when particle sizes are much smaller than the wavelength, equation [\[GL.dS\]](#) reduces to the so-called Schwarzschild equation:

$$\frac{dS_{\theta}(v, l)}{dl} = \sigma_a^{vol}(v, l)(J(v, l) - S_{\theta}(v, l))$$

this can be written in its integrated form as:

$$S_{\theta}(\nu, l_{obs}) = S_{\theta}(\nu, l_o) \tau(\nu, l_{obs}, l_o) + \int_{l_{obs}}^{l_o} J(\nu, l) \sigma_a^{vol}(\nu, l) \tau(\nu, l_{obs}, l) dl$$

where

$\tau(\nu, l_1, l_2)$ transmission between l_1 and l_2 for wavenumber ν (see Section [4.2.3](#))

4.2.1 Ray Tracing

The integration of Eq. [\[Gl.S\]](#) is performed along the line of sight of the instrument, which is, through atmospheric refraction, not a straight line. This integration is performed not analytically but numerically for thin atmospheric layers characterized by constant representative state parameters which are derived from the state parameter profiles by mass-weighted integration. In a medium of smoothly varying refractive index $n(z)$, there is refraction as soon as the gradient of $n(z)$ is not parallel to the raypath. After traveling the infinitesimal distance dl , the angular difference between the original and the new direction $d\theta$ is (Hase and Höpfner 1999)

$$d\theta = dl \times |\vec{e}_s \cdot \nabla n_b| / n_b,$$

where \vec{e}_s is the component of unity in direction perpendicular to the old direction and the gradient of refractive index. The length of each path segment l in layer j used for integration of Equation [\[Gl.mg\]](#) then is

$$l_j = \int dl$$

The slant path column amount m_g of a species g in the layer j is

$$m_g(l) = \int_{l_1}^{l_2} \rho_g(l) dl$$

where the particle density ρ_g of species g is calculated as

$$\rho_g(l) = C_{v,g} \cdot \frac{N_{avo}}{R} \cdot \frac{p(l)}{T_{kin}(l)}$$

where N_{avo} is the Avogadro constant, R the universal gas constant, $C_{v,g}$ the volume mixing ration of species g , $T_{kin}(l)$ kinetic temperature at the position l , and p is pressure.

Mass-weighted state parameters are

$$p_{average,g,l} = \frac{\int \frac{p\rho_g}{m_{g,j}}}{dl}$$

and

$$T_{average,g,l} = \frac{\int \frac{T \rho_g}{m_{g,j}} dl}{dl}$$

This approach supports straight forward consideration of ellipsoidal earth shape, where the local radius R_E is

$$R_E(\Psi) = \sqrt{\frac{a_E^2 \cdot b_E^2}{b_E^2 \cdot \cos^2 \Psi + a_E^2 \cdot \sin^2 \Psi}}$$

where

$$\tan \Psi = \left(\frac{b_E}{a_E} \right)^2 \tan \Phi$$

with geocentric latitude Ψ , geographic latitude Φ , major semiaxis a_E , and minor semiaxis b_E .

There is a variety of parameterizations for the refractive index. As an example, in KOPRA, the refractive index n_b is calculated from the wavenumber-dependent refractive index for dry air n_{B_o} , referring to reference state parameters $T_o = 288.16$ K and $p_o = 1013.25$ hPa, as

$$n_B(l) = \sqrt{\frac{2 k p(l) + T(l)}{T(l) - k p(l)}}$$

where

$$k = \frac{T_o (n_{B_o}^2 - 1)}{p_o (n_{B_o}^2 + 2)}$$

The wavenumber dependence of the refractive index is

$$(n_{B_o} - 1) \cdot 10^6 = 83.4213 + \frac{24060.3}{130 - 10^8 \nu^2} + \frac{159.97}{38.9 - 10^8 \nu^2}$$

where ν must be provided in cm^{-1} .

4.2.2 The Source Function

4.2.2.1 Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium

In the case of local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE), the source function J_{LTE} is the Planck function B of the kinetic temperature T_{kin} of the emitting medium:

$$J^{LTE}(\nu, l) = B(\nu, T_{kin}(l))$$

The Planck function as a function of frequency f is

$$B(f, T) = \frac{2f^2}{c^2} \cdot \frac{hf}{\exp\left(\frac{hf}{k_B T}\right) - 1}$$

where h is the Planck constant and c the velocity of light. The Planck function as a function of wavenumber ν can be deduced from Eq. [\[planckf\]](#) by post-differentiation of the Planck function by $\frac{d\nu}{df}$:

$$B(\nu, T_{kin}(l)) = \frac{2hc^2\nu^3}{\exp\left(\frac{h\nu}{k_B T_{kin}(l)}\right) - 1}$$

4.2.2.2 Non-Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium (NLTE)

Here we follow the formalism of (Edwards, López-Puertas, and López-Valverde 1993) and (Edwards, López-Puertas, and Mlynczak 1994). For a single line, the source function J in case of non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (NLTE) can be written as:

$$J^{NLTE}(\nu, l) = \frac{2hc^2\nu^3}{\frac{r_1}{r_2} \exp\left(\frac{h\nu}{k_B T_{kin}(l)}\right) - 1}$$

where r_1 and r_2 are the ratios of populations between the general (NLTE) and LTE cases for the lower (1) and upper (2) states of transition n . This ratio of populations between the general (NLTE) and LTE cases for the state m can also be written as

$$r_m = f_Q(l) \exp\left(-\frac{E_m}{k_B} \left(\frac{1}{T_{vib,m}(l)} - \frac{1}{T_{kin}(l)}\right)\right)$$

where m is the vibrational state under consideration, E_m its energy level, T_{vib} the related vibrational temperature, and $f_Q(l)$ is a correction factor to the vibrational partition sum given by

$$f_Q(l) = \frac{\sum_m g_m \exp\left(-\frac{hcE_m}{k_B T_{kin}(l)}\right)}{\sum_m g_m \exp\left(-\frac{hcE_m}{k_B T_{vib,m}(l)}\right)}$$

Here, g_m represents the degeneracy factor of state m . For superimposed lines, the NLTE source function is written as

$$J^{NLTE}(\nu, l) = \beta(\nu, l) \cdot B(\nu, T_{kin}(l))$$

$$\beta(\nu, l) = \frac{\sum_{gn} r_{2,gn}(l) \sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}(\nu, l) m_g(l)}{\sum_{gn} \alpha_{gn}(\nu, l) \sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}(\nu, l) m_g(l)}$$

$$\alpha_{gn} = \frac{\sigma_{a,gn}^{NLTE}(\nu, l)}{\sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}(\nu, l)}$$

where

$\sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}$ absorption coefficient (LTE) (see Eq. [\[Gl.AbLTE\]](#))

$\sigma_{a,gn}^{NLTE}$ absorption coefficient (NLTE) (see Eq. [\[Gl.AbNLTE\]](#))

4.2.3 Transmittance

The spectral atmospheric transmission $\tau(\nu, l_1, l_2)$ between two points l_1 and l_2 on the line of sight is calculated as follows:

$$\tau(\nu, l_1, l_2) = \exp - \left\{ \int_{l_1}^{l_2} \sigma_a^{Vol}(\nu, l) dl + \int_{l_1}^{l_2} \underbrace{\sigma_e^{Vol}(\nu, l)}_{\text{Aerosol}} dl \right\}$$

$$= \exp - \left\{ \sum_{g=1}^G \int_{l_1}^{l_2} \sigma_{a,g}(\nu, l) \rho_g(l) dl + \int_{l_1}^{l_2} \underbrace{\sigma_e^{Vol}(\nu, l)}_{\text{Aerosol}} dl \right\}$$

where

- $\sigma_{e,aerosol}^{Vol}$ aerosol extinction coefficient (from external Mie calculation)
- σ_a^{Vol} volume absorption coefficient (see Eq. [\[Gl.Volab\]](#))
- $\sigma_{a,g}$ absorption cross-section (sometimes also called absorption coefficient) of the gas g (see Eqs. [\[Gl.Abg\]](#))
- ρ_g particle density of species g (see Eq. [\[rho\]](#))
- dl path element
- G number of gases taken into account

4.2.3.1 Absorption Coefficients

4.2.3.1.1 Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium

The absorption coefficient (per volume) is

$$\sigma_a^{Vol}(\nu, l) = \sum_{g=1}^G \sigma_{a,g}(\nu, l) \cdot \rho_g(l)$$

The absorption cross-section of species g is split up in terms which are (1) calculated line-by-line by considering each transition, (2) directly provided (often as pressure-temperature dependent) cross-sections, and (3) parameterized continua to correct for deviations from a specific line-shape or parameterized absorption cross-sections)

$$\sigma_{a,g}(\nu, l) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_g} \sigma_{a,gn}(\nu, l) + (\text{Cross-Section-Gases}) + (\text{Kontinua})$$

where

- σ_a^{Vol} absorption coefficient (per volume)
- $\sigma_{a,gn}$ absorption cross-section of the transition n of species for gases g calculated line-by-line (see Eqs. [\[GI.AbLTE\]](#) / [\[GI.AbNLTE\]](#))
- ρ_g particle number density of species g (see Eq. [\[rho\]](#))
- G number of species under consideration
- N_g number of line-transitions of species g

The absorption cross-sections $\sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}$ of transition n of species g in LTE is written

$$\sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}(\nu, l) = A_{gn}(T_{kin}(l), \nu) \cdot \Phi_{gn}(\nu, p(l), T_{kin}(l))$$

where

- A_{gn} line intensity of transition n of species g (see Eq. [\[Linienint\]](#))
- Φ_{gn} profile function of transition n of species g at position l (see Eq. [\[Profilfunktionen\]](#))

4.2.3.1.2 Non-Local Thermodynamic Equilibrium

In case of NLTE, the absorption cross-section $\sigma_{a,gn}^{NLTE}$ of transition n of species g is derived from the absorption cross-section in LTE by a correction factor α :

$$\sigma_{a,gn}^{NLTE}(\nu, l) = \alpha_{gn}(\nu, l) \cdot \sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}(\nu, l)$$

Correction factor α , which is one in case of LTE, is calculated as

$$\alpha_{gn}(\nu, l) = \frac{\sigma_{a,gn}^{NLTE}(\nu, l)}{\sigma_{a,gn}^{LTE}(\nu, l)} = \frac{r_1 - r_2 \Gamma}{1 - \Gamma}$$

where

$$\Gamma = \frac{g_1 n_2}{g_2 n_1} = \exp(-h\nu/k_B T_{kin})$$

$$r_1 = \frac{n_1^{NLTE}}{n_1^{LTE}} \quad ; \quad r_2 = \frac{n_2^{NLTE}}{n_2^{LTE}}$$

and where

- r_1, r_2 ratios of populations between the general (NLTE) and LTE cases for the lower (1) and upper (2) state (see [\[rm\]](#))
- n_1^{NLTE} population of the lower state (NLTE)

- n_1^{LTE} population of the lower state (LTE)
 n_2^{NLTE} population of the upper state (NLTE)
 n_2^{LTE} population of the upper state (LTE)
 g_1, g_2 level statistical weights for the lower (1) and upper (2) state

4.2.3.1.3 Line Intensities

The intensity A_{gn} of line n of species g is

$$A_{gn}(T_{kin}(l), \nu) = A_{gn}(T'_o, \nu) \cdot \frac{Q(T'_o)}{Q(T_{kin}(l))} \frac{e^{-\frac{E''_{gn}}{k_B T_{kin}(l)}}}{e^{-\frac{E''_{gn}}{k_B T'_o}}} \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{h\nu}{k_B T_{kin}(l)}}}{1 - e^{-\frac{h\nu}{k_B T'_o}}}$$

where

- k_B Boltzmann constant
 E''_{gn} lower state energy of transition n (see Eq. (E''))
 $Q(T)$ LTE total internal partition function evaluated at T (see Eq. (Q))
 $Q(T'_o)$ LTE total internal partition function at T'_o
 $A_{gn}(T'_o)$ line intensity at reference temperature T'_o
 T_{kin} kinetic temperature
 $\nu_{o,n}$ central wavenumber of transition n
 T'_o reference temperature (296 K)
 ν wavenumber, usually approximated as $\nu_{o,n}$

The lower state energy E'' is calculated from the lower state energy e'' in units of wavenumbers as given in spectroscopic databases by:

$$E_{gn}'' = c e''_{gn} h$$

The total internal partition function $Q(T)$ describes the temperature dependence of the line intensity of a transition. In LTE it is

$$Q(T) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} g_j \exp\left(\frac{E_j}{k_B T}\right)$$

where j is the rotational-vibrational-state, g the factor of degeneration, and E the energy of level j . It is approximated as

$$Q(T) = a_0 + a_1 T + a_2 T^2 + a_3 T^3$$

where $a_0, a_1, a_2,$ and a_3 are pretabulated coefficients (Gamache, Hawkins, and Rothman 1990).

4.2.3.1.4 Profile Function

The Doppler profile function describes the statistical distribution of frequency shifts due to thermal motion:

$$\Phi_{D,n}(\nu, T) = \frac{1}{\alpha_{D,n}} \sqrt{\frac{\ln 2}{\pi}} e^{-\ln 2 \left(\frac{\nu - \nu_{o,n}}{\alpha_{D,n}} \right)^2}$$

where

$$\alpha_{D,n}(T) = \frac{\nu_{o,n}}{c} \sqrt{\frac{2k_B T \ln 2}{M}}$$

and where $\alpha_{D,n}$ is the Doppler halfwidth, M the molecular mass, and $\nu_{o,n}$ central wavenumber of transition n .

The Lorentzian profile function $\Phi_{L,n}$ of transition n , centered at $\nu_{o,n}$, describes pressure broadening, under assumption of infinitesimally short impact between collision partners and elastic collisions:

$$\Phi_{L,n}(\nu, p, T) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{\alpha_{L,n}}{(\nu - \nu_{o,n})^2 + \alpha_{L,n}^2} \right)$$

The actual Lorentzian halfwidth $\alpha_{L,n}$ is calculated for the actual temperature T and actual pressure p from the related reference Lorentzian halfwidth $\alpha_{L_o,n}$ measured at reference pressure p_o^L and reference temperature T_o^L

$$\alpha_{L,n}(p, T) = \alpha_{L_o,n}(p_o^L, T_o^L) \frac{p}{p_o^L} \left(\frac{T_o^L}{T} \right)^{\gamma_n}$$

The coefficient of temperature dependence of the halfwidth γ_n , which, following classical collisional theory, should be 0.5, may deviate from this theoretical value; therefore laboratory measurements are used whenever available.

The Lorentzian halfwidth is composed of a self-broadening term and a foreign broadening term:

$$\alpha_{L_o,n} = (1 - C_{V,g}) \alpha_{L_o,n}^{foreign} + C_{V,g} \alpha_{L_o,n}^{self}$$

where

- $\alpha_{L_o,n}$ reference Lorentzian halfwidth of transition n
- $\alpha_{L_o,n}^{foreign}$ reference foreign-broadening Lorentzian halfwidth of transition n of species g
- $\alpha_{L_o,n}^{self}$ reference self-broadening Lorentzian halfwidth of transition n of species g

$C_{V,g}$ volume mixing ratio of species g

The Voigt function $\Phi_{V,n}$ is the convolution of Doppler and Lorentzian broadening:

$$\Phi_{L,n}(v, p, T) \otimes \Phi_{D,n}(v, T)$$

$$\Phi_{V,n}(v, p, T) = \frac{1}{\alpha_{D,n}} \sqrt{\frac{\ln 2}{\pi}} \frac{y}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-t^2}}{(x-t)^2 + y^2} dt$$

where

$$y = \frac{\alpha_{L,n}}{\alpha_{D,n}} \sqrt{\ln 2}$$

and

$$x = \left(\frac{v - v_{o,n}}{\alpha_{D,n}} \right) \sqrt{\ln 2}$$

where $\alpha_{D,n}$ and $\alpha_{L,n}$ are Doppler and Lorentzian halfwidths, respectively, and $v_{o,n}$ is the central wavenumber of transition n .

4.2.3.1.5 Line-mixing

In the case of overlapping lines broadened by collisions, line mixing effects have to be taken into account. The Lorentzian line profile shape is then modified:

$$\Phi_{L,n}^{lm}(v, p, T) = \frac{\tilde{A}(T)}{A(T)} \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{L,n} + (v - \tilde{v}_{o,n})\tilde{Y}_n(T, p)}{(v - \tilde{v}_{o,n})^2 + (\tilde{\alpha}_{L,n})^2}$$

where

- $\Phi_{L,n}^{lm}$ pressure broadened profile function of transition n
under consideration of line-mixing
- $\tilde{A}(T)$ line mixing modified line intensity
- $A(T)$ line intensity (see Eq. [\[GLA\]](#))
- $\tilde{v}_{o,n}$ line-mixing modified central wavenumber
- $\tilde{\alpha}_{L,n}$ line mixing modified Lorentzian halfwidth
- \tilde{Y}_n line-mixing coefficient

The determination of the quantities signed by a tilde is discussed in Part VI in Stiller (2000). Within the Rosenkranz approximation valid for low atmospheric pressures, the quantities $\tilde{A}(T)$, $\tilde{v}_{o,n}$, and $\tilde{\alpha}_{L,n}$ are given by their unmodified values.

This modified shape of pressure-broadened lines maps into the Voigt line shape as follows:

$$\Phi_{V,n}^{lm}(\nu, p, T) = \sqrt{\frac{\ln 2}{\pi}} \frac{1}{\alpha_{D,n}} [K(\tilde{x}_n, \tilde{y}_n) + \tilde{Y}_n(p, T) L(\tilde{x}_n, \tilde{y}_n)]$$

$$K(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) = \frac{\tilde{y}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-t^2}}{(\tilde{x} - t)^2 + \tilde{y}^2} dt$$

$$L(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(\tilde{x} - t)e^{-t^2}}{(\tilde{x} - t)^2 + \tilde{y}^2} dt$$

$$\tilde{x} = \left(\frac{\nu - \tilde{\nu}_{o,n}}{\alpha_{D,n}} \right) \sqrt{\ln 2}$$

$$\tilde{y} = \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{L,n}}{\alpha_{D,n}} \sqrt{\ln 2}$$

where

- $\Phi_{V,n}^{lm}$ Voigt profile function of transition n
under consideration of line-mixing
- $\alpha_{D,n}$ Doppler halfwidth (see Eq. [\[DopplerH\]](#))
- \tilde{Y}_n line-mixing coefficient

4.2.3.1.6 χ -Faktor

The impact of time-dependence of collisions on the line shape is considered by empirical χ -factors (Clough, Kneizys, and Davies 1989)

$$\Phi_{\chi}(\nu) = \chi \cdot \Phi_V(\nu, p, T)$$

where

- Φ_V Voigt-profile function [cm] (see [\[Gl.PhiV\]](#))
- χ χ -factor

Table 1: χ -factor for CO₂ self-broadening; $\Delta\nu = \nu - \nu_{o,n}$, $\nu_{o,n}$ is the central wavenumber of transition n , and K_1 is the modified Bessel function of the second kind

Temperature: 296 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 1$
$3 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 1.470 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{7.782}\right)$

Temperature: 296 K	
$10 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.535 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{36.535}\right)$
	$ \Delta\nu \geq 120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$\Delta\nu < 0$	$\Delta\nu > 0$
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.889 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{31.627}\right)$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.220 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{50.063}\right)$
Temperature: 218 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 1$
$3 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 1.240319 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{13.9296}\right)$
$10 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.68 \frac{ \Delta\nu }{28} K_1\left(\frac{ \Delta\nu }{28}\right)$
	$ \Delta\nu \geq 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$\Delta\nu < 0$	$\Delta\nu > 0$
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 10.04385 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{21.233306}\right)$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2} = 0.345 \exp\left(-\frac{ \Delta\nu }{43.448}\right)$

For CO₂, asymmetric χ -factors have to be considered. χ -factors for CO₂ self-broadening as published by Refs. (Doucen et al. 1985; V. Menoux, Doucen, and Boulet 1987a; Victor Menoux et al. 1991) are compiled in Table 4.1. χ -factors for CO₂ foreign-broadening by N₂ as published by Refs. (Cousin et al. 1985; V. Menoux, Doucen, and Boulet 1987b; Victor Menoux et al. 1991) and used in KOPRA are compiled in Table 4.2.

Table 2: χ -factor for CO₂-broadening by N₂

Temperature: 296 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 0.5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1$
$0.5 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1.064 \exp(-0.1235 \Delta\nu)$
$20 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.125 \exp(-0.0164 \Delta\nu)$
$50 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.146 \exp(-0.0196 \Delta\nu)$
	$ \Delta\nu \geq 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$\Delta\nu < 0$	$\Delta\nu > 0$
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1.8593 \exp(-0.03776 \Delta\nu)$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.146 \exp(-0.0196 \Delta\nu)$
Temperatur: 238 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1$
$5 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 22 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1.968 \exp(-0.1354 \Delta\nu)$
$22 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.160 \exp(-0.0214 \Delta\nu)$
$ \Delta\nu \geq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.162 \exp(-0.0216 \Delta\nu)$
Temperature: 193 K	

Temperature: 296 K

$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 9 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1$
$9 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 23 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 3.908 \exp(-0.1514 \Delta\nu)$
$23 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 28 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.207 \exp(-3.778 \cdot 10^{-3} \Delta\nu)$
$28 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.219 \exp(-0.0276 \Delta\nu)$
$\Delta\nu < 0$	$\Delta\nu > 0$
$50 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$50 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 135 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.20894 \exp(-0.026694 \Delta\nu)$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 0.146 \exp(-0.0196 \Delta\nu)$
$130 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 160 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$ \Delta\nu > 135 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 2.824997 \exp(-0.0467266 \Delta\nu)$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1.164 \exp(-0.035 \Delta\nu)$
$ \Delta\nu > 160 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} = 1.192053 \exp(-0.0413334 \Delta\nu)$	

The χ -factor for CO₂ foreign broadening by O₂ as published by (Cousin et al. 1985) and (V. Menoux, Doucen, and Boulet 1987b) is compiled in Table [4.3](#).

Table 3: χ -factor for CO₂-broadening by O₂

Temperature: 296 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 1$
$3 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 3.341 \exp(-0.4021 \Delta\nu)$
$8 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.155 \exp(-0.0179 \Delta\nu)$
$50 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 70 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.238 \exp(-0.0266 \Delta\nu)$
$70 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.146 \exp(-0.0196 \Delta\nu)$
$ \Delta\nu \geq 140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	
$\Delta\nu < 0$	$\Delta\nu > 0$
$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 1.8593 \exp(-0.03776 \Delta\nu)$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.146 \exp(-0.0196 \Delta\nu)$
Temperature: 238 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 1$
$5 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 22 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 1.968 \exp(-0.1354 \Delta\nu)$
$22 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.160 \exp(-0.0214 \Delta\nu)$
$ \Delta\nu \geq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.162 \exp(-0.0216 \Delta\nu)$
Temperature: 193 K	
$0 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 11 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 1$
$11 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 23 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 7.908 \exp(-0.188 \Delta\nu)$
$23 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 35 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.122 - (7.539 \cdot 10^{-4} \Delta\nu)$
$35 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.349 \exp(-0.0369 \Delta\nu)$
$50 \leq \Delta\nu \leq 135 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$\chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 0.129 \exp(-0.0170 \Delta\nu)$

Temperature: 296 K

$$|\Delta\nu| \geq 135 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad \chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2} = 1.455 \exp(-0.0350 |\Delta\nu|)$$

These χ -factors are added weighted by the partial pressures p_{CO_2} , p_{N_2} and p_{O_2} of contributing gases CO_2 , N_2 and O_2 :

$$\frac{p_{\text{CO}_2}}{p_{\text{total}}} \cdot \chi_{\text{CO}_2} + \frac{p_{\text{N}_2}}{p_{\text{total}}} \cdot \chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-N}_2} + \frac{p_{\text{O}_2}}{p_{\text{total}}} \cdot \chi_{\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2}$$

where

$$p_{\text{total}} = p_{\text{CO}_2} + p_{\text{N}_2} + p_{\text{O}_2}$$

4.2.4 Field of View and Instrumental Line Shape

While previous sections deal with radiative processes in the atmosphere which are independent of the observing system, in the following the influence of the observing system is discussed.

4.2.4.1 Instrumental Line Shape

The instrument line shape (ILS) is a function the atmospheric spectrum has to be convolved with in order to simulate what is seen by the instrument:

$$S_{\theta}^{\text{AILS}}(\nu, l_{\text{obs}}) = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{\theta}(\nu', l_{\text{obs}}) \cdot \text{AILS}(\nu - \nu') d\nu'}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \text{AILS}(\nu - \nu') d\nu'}$$

where

S_{θ}	spectral radiance for viewing angle θ
AILS	apparatus function incl. numerical apodization (apodized instrumental line shape) (see Part XI of (Stiller 2000))
$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \text{AILS}(\nu - \nu') d\nu'$	normalization

KOPRA determines a single sided ($x \geq 0$) and complex-valued modulation efficiency with symmetric real and antisymmetric imaginary parts. The AILS is the Fourier transform of the modulation efficiency. The modulation efficiency $M(x)$ includes the numeric apodization function, the modulation loss due to self apodization, the linear modulation loss and the phase error.

$$\text{AILS}(\nu) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} M(x) e^{-i\nu x} dx$$

with

$$M(x) = M_{\text{resolution}}(x) \times M_{\text{numeric}}(x) \times M_{\text{self}}(x) \times M_{\text{linear}}(x) \times M_{\text{phase}}(x)$$

- resolution

The interferogram is restricted to maximal optical path difference L

$$M_{resolution}(x) = 1 \quad \text{if} \quad |x| \leq L$$

$$M_{resolution}(x) = 0 \quad \text{else}$$

- apodization function

- a. sinc

$$M_{numeric} = 1$$

- b. triangle

$$M_{numeric} = 1 - |x|/L$$

- c. Hamming

$$M_{numeric} = 0.53856 + 0.46144 \times \cos(\pi \times x/L)$$

- d. Blackmann-Harris 3-term

$$M_{numeric} = 0.42323 + 0.49755 \times \cos(\pi \times x/L) + 0.07922 \times \cos(2 \times \pi \times x/L)$$

- e. Blackmann-Harris 4-term

$$M_{numeric} = 0.35875 + 0.48829 \times \cos(\pi \times x/L)$$

$$+ 0.14128 \times \cos(2 \times \pi \times x/L)$$

$$+ 0.01168 \times \cos(3 \times \pi \times x/L)$$

- f. Norton-Beer weak

$$M_{numeric} = 0.384093 - 0.087577 \times (1 - (x/L)^2) + 0.703484 \times (1 - (x/L)^2)^2$$

- g. Norton-Beer medium

$$M_{numeric} = 0.152442 - 0.136176 \times (1 - (x/L)^2) + 0.983734 \times (1 - (x/L)^2)^2$$

- h. Norton-Beer strong

$$M_{numeric} = 0.045335 - 0.554883 \times (1 - (x/L)^2)^2 + 0.399782 \times (1 - (x/L)^2)^4$$

- self apodization

The interferometer has finite acceptance angle. It can be shown, that the optical path difference depends on the inclination of the wavefront versus the optical axis. In case of homogeneously illuminated circular internal FOV of semidiameter one finds that this leads to an additional loss of modulation:

$$M_{self} = \frac{\sin(\pi \times \Delta v \times x)}{\pi \times \Delta v \times x} \text{ with } \Delta v = 0.5 \times v \times \alpha^2$$

Note that the self apodization (and thereby the resulting AILS) depends on spectral position v . The additional modulation loss describes the consequences of the finite acceptance angle not completely. In addition, the spectral abscissa is scaled by $0.5 \times (\cos(\alpha) + 1)$.

- linear modulation loss

This term is used to model the width of the imperfect AILS.

$$M_{linear} = 1 - (1 - a) \times x/L$$

the factor a gives the modulation efficiency at maximal path difference vs ideal instrument.

- phase error

This term is used to model the asymmetry of the imperfect AILS. The phase error φ is given in radians.

$$M_{phase} = \frac{e^{-i\varphi}}{\cos(\varphi)}$$

The norm of the AILS is fixed by the real part of $M(0)$. The denominator ensures the norm to be unity.

Since the real valued AILS is the Fourier transform of the complex-valued modulation efficiency, the latter is symmetric in the real part and antisymmetric in the imaginary part. Due to this symmetry, the AILS is fully determined by a single sided modulation efficiency interferogram.

4.2.5 SEDF (Field-of-view)

The observed spectral radiance $S_{\theta_0}^{SEDF}(\nu, l_{obs})$ is the convolution of the radiances related to observation angles θ with the weighting function W describing the SEDF (patial energy distribution function, often called also field-of-view, FOV).

$$S_{\theta_0}^{SEDF}(\nu, l_{obs}) = \int_{-\theta_{max}}^{\theta_{max}} S_{\theta}^{AILS}(\nu, l_{obs}) W(\theta - \theta_0) d\theta$$

where

$W(\theta - \theta_0)$	weighting function related SEDF as integrated for horizontal stripes $d\theta$	
$S_{\theta_0}^{SEDF}$	SEDF-convolved spectral radiance for viewing angle θ_0 $\left[\frac{W}{cm^2 sr \cdot cm^{-1}} \right]$	
$SEDF$	spatial energy distribution function	
S_{θ}^{AILS}	spectral radiance convolved by apodized instrumental line shape	(see Section 4.2.4.1)
l_{obs}	position of the observer [cm]	
ν	wavenumber (wavenumber) [cm^{-1}]	
S_{θ}	spectral radiance for infinitesimal viewing angle θ	

θ	viewing angle
θ_{max}	maximum angle covered by FOV

4.2.5.1 SEDF - some more details

(Mind that in this section, S^{SEDF} is substituted by I , S^{ALLS} by r and W by s .)

A radiance measurement at a given spectral wavenumber of a (binned) detector pixel collects radiances arriving from different angles depending on the optics of the instrument. One typically defines the location of the center of the detector pixel in geophysical coordinates (typically rounded to the center of the detector for simplification) and needs to compute the spherical integral over the pointwise multiplication from the SEDF function s given the angular sensitivity of the pixel and the incoming radiance r :

$$I(\nu) = \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \int_0^{2\pi} c \cos(\theta) s(\nu, \phi, \theta) r(\nu, \phi, \theta) d\phi d\theta$$

Typically, one does not expect a relevant change in radiation in the azimuthal direction such that one neglects this in the computation. In particular, often the atmospheric discretization does not allow for horizontal variation. The simplified version is:

$$I(\nu) = \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} s(\nu, \theta) r(\nu, \theta) d\theta$$

The task of the forward model is now to provide the function r . This has to be discretized as well such that r is only evaluated for a discrete set of angles $\{\theta_i\}_{i=0\dots n}$. The function s is often given in analytic fashion or on a much finer grid that is feasible to evaluate r on. To reduce errors of the following numerical integration, one assumes a linear behaviour of r between samples, which is a reasonable for a proper choice of gridding. So r is approximated with the help of the triangular functions tri

$$\text{tri}_i(\theta) = \begin{cases} (\theta - \theta_{i-1}) / (\theta_i - \theta_{i-1}), & \theta_{i-1} \leq \theta < \theta_i; \\ (\theta_{i+1} - \theta) / (\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i), & \theta_i \leq \theta < \theta_{i+1}; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

as

$$r(\nu, \theta) \approx \sum_{i=0}^n \text{tri}_i(\theta) r(\nu, \theta_i).$$

Thus the integral can be approximated as

$$\begin{aligned}
I(\nu) &\approx \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} s(\nu, \theta) \sum_{i=0}^n \text{tri}_i(\theta) r(\nu, \theta_i) d\theta \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^n r(\nu, \theta_i) \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} s(\theta) \text{tri}_i(\theta) d\theta \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^n \overset{=w_i(\nu)}{w_i(\nu)} r(\nu, \theta_i)
\end{aligned}$$

with precomputed weights $w_i(\nu)$. In limb sounding one always has many radiance measurements taken by different (binned) pixels with differing functions s , but in computation, one can reuse the same set of radiance computations $r(\nu, \theta_i)$ and combine them with different weights. One typically uses a fixed grid of angles, typically oversampled in relation to the grid defined by the actual measurements and extend to both upper and lower end. For wavenumbers ν close to each other, one often neglects the differences, as the SEDF typically does not vary strongly spectrally. Thus one normally uses one set of weights for all radiances within a small wavenumber region.

Figure 4: A simplified cartoon showing how radiances at different angles contribute to two measurements (green and blue).

A simplified example of this is depicted in Fig. 4.1. Radiances r are evaluated on a fixed angular grid, here 0.01° . Two measurements shall be simulated here with SEDF functions shown in green and blue. In the cartoon, the weights are not computed properly, but approximated by sampling the value of the function s at the relevant angle to simplify the visual depiction. Proper weights will deviate slightly; the relevance of proper computation becomes obviously the more relevant the less oversampling in angle one uses.

4.3 Jacobians

The forward model must not only compute the radiances but also provide derivatives (or Jacobians) with respect to all relevant input parameters. That are all retrieval targets including parameters of simplified instrument model such as offset, gain, and/or viewing angles.

The efficient computation of Jacobian is key for tomographic retrievals either by analytic (i.e. the manual derivation and implementation into code alongside or within the regular routines) or employing adjoint methods (e.g. Lotz, Naumann, and Ungermann 2012). Using finite differences is too slow and can (and should) only be used for validation of the more advanced methods. Beyond that, the section for calculating analytical Jacobians in forward models of Carli et al. (2020) as well as chapter XIII of Stiller (2000) are still valid.

5 The measurement error covariance

See Section on "Calculation of the VCM of the measurements for forward models" of Carli et al. (2020) for a detailed description. In addition, potential correlation between individual pixels might be taken into account.

Generally, the covariance matrix of the measurements is required for the retrieval. While the errors of individual samples of the interferogram are likely uncorrelated, processing steps like apodization of the interferogram or zero-filling the spectrum introduce strong correlations between neighbouring pixels that need to be taken into account. These correlations drop off quickly such that the correlations of different microwindows can often be neglected. Either way, the resulting matrix is a block-diagonal matrix, a structure, which must be exploited for both storage and inversion by the program to save computational time and memory.

To properly set up the matrix, the noise model of the instrument and the processing needs to be closely examined to propagate the introduced correlations forward, which is described in the reference above

6 The regularisation

Typically, the measurements do not contain sufficient information to fully determine the retrieved state space. The measurements are necessarily of finite nature and the atmospheric state is a priori of a continuous nature. The discretization described in Chap. 3 reduces the atmospheric state space to a finite dimensional vector, but often this is not sufficient to either fully determine the state space from the measurements alone or to have a retrieval result that is not dominated by noise. This problem is typically solved by approximating the original problem by a problem, which is well-posed, e.g., by adding additional so called a priori information to the problem restricting the degrees of freedoms of the state space until the available measurements are sufficient to determine a physically sensible solution.

In the atmospheric sciences, one often uses the Bayesian approach by injecting statistical information about the atmospheric state into the problem. Almost all typically used regularisation schemes such as optimal estimation or Tikhonov regularisation can be interpreted in this framework.

To simplify the math and help in understanding, we first discuss a regularization for a one-dimensional problem before extending this to 2-D problems.

6.1 1-D Regularization

The original minimization problem of fitting an atmospheric state until the simulations agree with the measurements was enhanced already by the regularisation term Φ . Here, a single $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is

added to demonstrate the nature of the approximation. For $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ the problem approaches the unregularized problem, for $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, the Φ dominates the solution and the measurements have no influence anymore.

$$\min_f \left(\|F(f) - y\|_2^2 + \lambda \Phi(f) \right),$$

To define Φ , one often needs to be able to differentiate f , so we restrict f to lie within a Sobolev space, i.e., $f \in W^1$.

If we capture our a priori knowledge about f in a covariance function $C(t, t'): \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$, Φ can be associated with the related norm, i.e. $\Phi(f) = \|f\|_C = \|C^{-1/2}f\|$. If f has an expected value of f_a not equal to the zero function, one subtracts this previously, i.e.,

$$\min_f \left(\|F(f) - y\|_2^2 + \|f - f_a\|_C \right),$$

is the general problem considered here. In case of a commonly assumed exponential covariance function C_e , i.e.,

$$C_e(t, t') = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{|t - t'|}{L}\right),$$

with standard deviation σ and correlation length L , the associated norm can be approximated as (Tarantola 2004, sec. 7.21)

$$\|f\|_{C_e} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left(\int \frac{1}{L} (f(x))^2 dx + \int L \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (f(x)) \right)^2 dx \right) = \frac{1}{L\sigma^2} (\|f\|_2^2 + L^2 \|f'\|_2^2).$$

In practice, one seldom operates on functions, but operates instead on a discretized version with covariance matrices (i. e., $S_a \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$) instead of covariance functions. In this case, the associated norm can be quickly computed using the inverse of the covariance matrix, the precision matrix S_a^{-1} . This gives the more common form of

$$\min_x (F(x) - y)^T S_e^{-1} (F(x) - y) + (x - x_a)^T S_a^{-1} (x - x_a)$$

However, for tomographic problems the task of inverting the matrix S_a might be computationally infeasible, whereas the direct construction as described above is a very simple task both in terms of required computational power and of memory storage needed. Thus, we show here, how the functional norm can be discretized to effectively directly construct (an approximation of) the inverse of the covariance matrix (also called a precision matrix).

Let $(x_i) = x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ the vector of sample positions, then the integral can be computed using the trapezoid sum:

$$\int_{x_0}^{x_n} f(x)^2 dx \approx \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (x_{i+1} - x_i) \left(\frac{f(x_{i+1})^2 + f(x_i)^2}{2} \right)$$

The integral shall be computed by a matrix-vector multiplication operating on the vector $(f(x_i)) = v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, e.g.

$$\frac{1}{\sigma^2 L} \| f \|_2^2 \approx \langle L_0 v, L_0 v \rangle = \| L_0 v \|_2^2$$

This can be accomplished by reformulating the sum above to operate on v_i and taking the square root. For a equidistant discretization with $h = x_1 - x_0$ this matrix L_0 can be defined as

$$L_0 = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{c}} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{h}{2} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & h & 0 & \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & \frac{h}{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

For the first order derivative, one can exploit that the forward differences correspond to the integral over the derivative over the interval. This allows the corresponding L_1 matrix to compute $\frac{L}{\sigma^2} \| f' \|_2^2 \approx \| L_1 v \|_2^2$ to be computed as:

$$L_1 = \frac{\sqrt{c}}{\sigma\sqrt{h}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The regularisation can be made altitude dependent by supplying not a single σ , but one for each altitude level, and/or by providing not a single c , but one for each *interval* between altitude levels.

The similarity to "pure" Tikhonov-Philips regularisation is apparent and one can, obviously, choose norms independent of any given covariance function (event though different typical choices have an obvious correlation in either the random walk or the exponential covariance). A general form that must be supported by the underlying retrieval software is defined as

$$\Phi(f) = \frac{1}{l\sigma^2} (\lambda_0 \| f \|_2^2 + L^2 \lambda_1 \| f' \|_2^2),$$

with tuning parameters σ , l , λ_0 , and λ_1 that will be defined depending on the level 2 target.

All these L -matrices described above have been implemented in JUTIL (JUelich Tomographic Inverstion Library; (Ungermann and Caron 2023)) for non-equidistant, rectilinear grids and varying standard deviations and correlation lengths.

6.2 2-D Regularization

The discussion above applies in principle also for the regularization of cross-section retrievals, but the function needs to be integrated over two axis. In particular, the correlation length is typically chosen differently for the two axis, so it is defined as L_x and L_z . The correlation coefficients can be seen as a transformation of the anisotropic 2-D space to an isotropic 2-D space, where variations in vertical and horizontal direction are similar.

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi(f) &= \frac{1}{L_x L_z \sigma^2} \left(\int_{x_0}^{x_{n_x}} \int_{z_0}^{z_{n_z}} f(x, z)^2 dx dz + \int_{x_0}^{x_{n_x}} \int_{z_0}^{z_{n_z}} L_x^2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} f(x, z) \right)^2 dx dz \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{x_0}^{x_{n_x}} \int_{z_0}^{z_{n_z}} L_z^2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z} f(x, z) \right)^2 dx dz \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{L_x L_z \sigma^2} \left(\|f\|_2^2 + L_x^2 \left\| \frac{\partial f(x, z)}{\partial x} \right\|_2^2 + L_z^2 \left\| \frac{\partial f(x, z)}{\partial z} \right\|_2^2 \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Please note that this does not directly relate to an exponential covariance in 2-D, which, sadly, cannot be expressed without using fractional derivatives that are impossible to compute using finite differences.

Adding again tuning parameters λ_0 , $\lambda_{1,x}$, and $\lambda_{1,z}$ to switch individual terms on and off or regulate its effect, the necessarily supported form is

$$\Phi(f) = \frac{1}{L_x L_z \sigma^2} \left(\lambda_0 \|f\|_2^2 + L_x^2 \lambda_{1,x} \left\| \frac{\partial f(x, z)}{\partial x} \right\|_2^2 + L_z^2 \lambda_{1,z} \left\| \frac{\partial f(x, z)}{\partial z} \right\|_2^2 \right)$$

The JUTIL package has reference implementations for the matrices for rectilinear 2-D grids and spatially varying standard deviation and correlations length (Ungermann and Caron 2023).

7 Optimization

This chapter deals with solving the minimization problems described above. We assume here a discretized problem with an atmospheric state $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, forward model F and precision matrices $S_\epsilon^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ and $S_a^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. S_a^{-1} can be constructed either by inverting an actual covariance matrix or be approximated by L -matrices as described in Chapter 6. That is, we assume that the minimization problem can be brought to the form of $J: \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$:

$$\min_x J(x) = \min_x \left((F(x) - y)^T S_\epsilon^{-1} (F(x) - y) + (x - x_a)^T S_a^{-1} (x - x_a) \right)$$

As F is a non-linear function, this requires an iterative solver. The trust-region based Newton-type methods are ideally suited to this task (e.g. Nocedal and Wright 2006). The most commonly algorithm of this class is the Levenberg-Marquardt method. I.e. we have a series of atmospheric states $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with

$$x_{i+1} = x_i - J''(x_i)^{-1} J'(x_i),$$

where we approximate the second derivative of J by neglecting the second derivatives of F (Gauss-Newton approximation):

$$x_{i+1} = x_i - \left(F'(x_i)^T S_\epsilon^{-1} F'(x_i) + S_a^{-1} + \lambda H \right)^{-1} \left(F'(x_i)^T S_\epsilon^{-1} (F(x_i) - y) + S_a^{-1} (x_i - x_a) \right)$$

Here, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $H \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are given as example on how to add the trust-region Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. Due to the large scale nature of the problem, the matrix inverse in the problem above should not be computed. Instead a linear equation system shall be solved with an iterative algorithm that solely requires the computation of matrix-vector products such as the conjugate-gradient scheme (including appropriate preconditioning schemes). Both the

computation of the matrix-matrix products as well as the inversion could otherwise dominate both memory consumption and computation time as all involved matrices should be set up in a memory-conserving sparse fashion, whereas the product of these matrices will be dense.

The Levenberg-Marquardt method requires typically a (series of) exact solution to the linear equation system. When the conjugate gradient scheme is employed to generate these, a more effective method is to store intermediate, approximate solutions during the conjugate gradient iteration scheme and modify the stopping criteria according to the overall convergence. Normally, a new equation system is given with a stronger regularization when an exact solution does not decrease the objective function, which requires another, costly, solution to this system; exploiting the conjugate gradient method, all these solutions are generated in one go, and more cheaply at that; in particular as the approximate solutions required in the first iterations are very cheaply to generate using the conjugate gradient method in contrast to an exact one (orders of magnitude cheaper). See Appendix B of Ungermann et al. (2010) for details of this computation time saving method.

These optimization methods have a reference implementation in Ungermann and Caron (2023) including examples.

7.1 Sequential retrievals

The linear equation systems posed by the Gauss-Newton and Levenberg-Marquardt algorithms become problematic to handle due to the sheer size of the tomographic problems. One approach to make these sub-problems easier is to replace a single, large equation system by a number of smaller ones. If the set of measurements can be split into groups, which are not correlated with one another, the measurement covariance matrix S_ϵ is diagonal or block-diagonal and each such group of measurements can be treated separately.

The Newton-Kaczmarz algorithm (Burger and Kaltenbacher 2006), which is also called algebraic reconstruction technique (ART) or sequential updating (Rodgers 2000, 2:97f)¹, splits each iteration of the Gauss-Newton algorithm into a sequence of updates to the atmospheric state. Effectively, it modifies the normal Newton iteration by using the Kaczmarz (1937) algorithm for solving the linear equation system. This method was successfully used by Steck et al. (2005) for 2-D tomographic evaluation of MIPAS data.

The measurements are split into q , $1 < q \leq m$, groups of measurements y^j , $1 \leq j \leq q$, so that no measurement of one group is correlated with any measurement of any other group. This implies that S_ϵ can be split without loss of information into q matrices $S^{j\epsilon}$ and also F is split into q sub-functions F^j . Each single iteration step is sub-divided into q steps. The vector $x_{i+1,0}$ is initialised with x_a and $S_{a,0}^{-1}$ with S_a^{-1} . The first linearisation point x_0 may be initialised with x_a or any other initial guess. A single “inner” iteration is then defined by:

¹ Both the original printing and the 2008 revision of (Rodgers 2000) contain errors in this section. Please refer to the erratas for a correct description.

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{i,j+1} &= x_{i,j} - \left(F_j^T(x_i) S_{\epsilon,j}^{-1} F_j'(x_i) + S_{a,j}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \cdot \\
 &\quad \left(S_{a,j}^{-1} (x_i - x_a) + F_j^T(x_i) S_{\epsilon,j}^{-1} (F(x_i) - y) \right) \\
 S_{a,j+1}^{-1} &= F_j^T(x_i) S_{\epsilon,j}^{-1} F_j'(x_i) + S_{a,j}^{-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The new “outer” state x_{i+1} is then defined by $x_{i,q}$. The linear equation systems that need to be solved for this method are much smaller, ideally being reduced

to a single line requiring only a single division to be solved. However, as $S_{a,j}^{-1}$ are dense matrices that need to be stored and updated, the memory consumption of this method is still substantial.

However, with respect to required computation time, a slight modification of this method has several advantages. As in limb sounding, most information of a profile comes from a single image, the convergence speed can be drastically improved. Normally 5 to 10 outer iterations are needed. When another inner loop is added, which updates the linearisation point according to the current result, the method delivers very useful results in a single outer iteration. This has practical advantages for some radiative transfer models:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{i,j,k+1} &= x_{i,j,k} - \left(F_j^T(x_{i,j,k}) S_{\epsilon,j}^{-1} F_j'(x_{i,j,k}) + S_{a,j}^{-1} \right)^{-1} \cdot \\
 &\quad \left(S_{a,j}^{-1} (x_i - x_a) + F_j^T(x_{i,j,k}) S_{\epsilon,j}^{-1} (F(x_i) - y) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

This new iteration performs several updates until the state change is minimal, e.g. needing r iterations. The update is performed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_{i,j+1,0} &= x_{i,j,r} \\
 S_{a,j+1}^{-1} &= F_j^T(x_{i,j,k}) S_{\epsilon,j}^{-1} F_j'(x_{i,j,k}) + S_{a,j}^{-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

and one proceeds with the middle iterations. The outer iteration may require only a single pass to achieve sufficient convergence.

8 Diagnostics

See Ungermann (2013) and Krasauskas et al. (2019) for a treatment on how to compute all usual diagnostics for large-scale retrievals with either direct methods for individual points (or the whole state space for sufficiently small retrievals) and Monte-Carlo methods for all points for arbitrarily large setups. These diagnostics include systematic uncertainties (e.g. due to pointing uncertainty, uncertainty in background gases, uncertainty in instrument gain/offset), random uncertainties (e.g. measurement noise), but also helpful quantities such as spatial resolution of derived quantities or measurement contribution (diagnosing the influence of regularisation on the result).

While diagnostics based on Monte-Carlo and method can be generated for every retrieval, diagnostics requiring a matrix inversion (such as the averaging kernel diagnostic of resolution) can only be computed for representative profiles or will require additional approximations or simplification.

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